

A Proposed Cyber Security Certification Scheme for Supply Chain Services

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Abstract — In this paper we outline the main elements of the proposed Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Supply Chain Services (SCS) as proposed by the EC project CYRENE [1]. The proposed CYRENE-EUSCS scheme used the published European Cybersecurity Certification scheme [2] as a template and the proposed EU scheme for cloud services [3] as an example. The CYRENE-EUSCS scheme aims to enhance the level of security of the SCS components including: business partners, processes/sub-processes, physical and cyber assets (hosted by different business partners).

Keywords—Supply Chain Service, European Cybersecurity Certification, Security, Conformity Assessment, Assurance

Introduction

The EU regulation 2019/881, known as Cybersecurity Act (CSA) [4] for cybersecurity certification, seeks to prevent market fragmentation and to make it easier for users to know to what extent ICT products (systems, devices, services, processes) are secure. The certification will attest that ICT products are certified in accordance to their schemes and comply with specified cybersecurity requirements. The proposal of NIS Directive 2.0 [5] contains measures for improving cybersecurity infrastructure; one of the key elements of the Commission's proposal is to address the security of supply chains and supplier relationships by requiring individual companies to address cybersecurity risks in supply chains and supplier relationships. Cybersecurity certification of the SCS can be con-

sidered as a mitigation action against cybersecurity SCS risks.

CYRENE's EUSCS scheme is using the European Cybersecurity Certification scheme, EUCC as a template and the EU scheme for cloud services, EUCS but will also incorporate the notion of the escalating vulnerability assessment level in bond with the different assurance levels. More specifically, the higher the assurance level will be, the deeper the vulnerability analysis will be performed. Users of the scheme may be supply chain service providers who wish to assess the security of their supply chain services through third-party certification. They can use the EUSCS scheme:

- to assess how a supply chain service meets the requirements of a predefined set of security control objectives and a related set of measures, when used according to security recommendations provided by the business partners and agreed by them;
- to provide business partners the information required to make informed choices about the procurement and operation of supply chain services (including processes, assets, technologies and operators involved in the provision of the supply chain services), and to allow business partners to use certified supply chain services in their own development activities, and to meet their own security compliance requirements.

The paper is structured as follows: Section II presents the state of play of the cybersecurity certification in the European Union (EU). In section III, the relevant standards we

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considered for preparing the CYRENE-EUSCS are described. In section IV, the assurance levels offered by the scheme are introduced. Section V presents the evaluation method and criteria defined in security objectives and requirements set for supply chains. Rules for compliance monitoring of SCSs security requirements are analysed in Section VI while Section VII presents the vulnerability handling and disclosure process. Finally, section VIII draws the conclusions of the current work and presents our future research directions.

Cybersecurity Certification in the EU

The EU cybersecurity certification is defined as a comprehensive set of rules, technical requirements, standards, and procedures that are established at the Union level and that apply to the certification or Conformity Assessment (CA) of specific ICT products. Each certification scheme shall specify the categories of products and services covered; the cybersecurity requirements that need to be met -such as standards or technical specifications-, the type of evaluation that is planned to be - done such as self-assessment or third party - and the intended level of assurance that is going to be achieved. The certificates will be valid across all Member States (MSs)

The EUCC

The EUCC will serve as a template to propose security certification schemes for ICT products. The EUCC scheme is based upon Article 54 of the CSA. The latter presents in detail the key elements that an EU certification scheme shall include.

Using the EUCC, any ICT product can serve as a Target of Evaluation (ToE) and can be the subject of a security evaluation also known as conformity assessment (CA) in which it is assessed against security requirements. The CA of the ToE is defined as the procedure that is followed for evaluating whether specified requirements relating to the ToE have been fulfilled. That being said, throughout the CA process, the ToE should be identified and security aspects should be concretely specified. The EUCC presents the key elements (e.g. category of product, cybersecurity requirements, standards, conformity assessment) that EU certification schemes shall include in all sectors. In this paper, the SCS is presented as a ToE for a CA process and based on the CC the security and assurance requirements for a SCS certification are identified. The SCS-ToE can be described from a business view (describing only the interconnected business partners and processes), the holistic technical view (capturing in addition all the physical and cyber assets participating in the SCS-processes) and the sector-specific technical view (snap-shot of the technical view that an individual partner adopts) [6], [7]. For preparing the CYRENE-EUSCS, the

EUCC was utilised as a template and the EUCC as an example. The risk-based identification of security and assurance requirements described in the methodology for sectoral cybersecurity assessments by ENISA was also used for preparing the CYRENE-EUSCS [8].

Use of Standards

The scheme proposes compliance with the following standards depending on the assessment we need to conduct.

- **For risk assessment**, ISO 2700x series of standards [9] also known as Information Security Management System (ISMS) Family of Standards is proposed. This helps organisations to develop and implement a framework in order to manage information security risks and controls of their information assets as well as to prepare themselves to assess it.

- **For conformity assessment**, ISO 15408 [10] and ISO 18045 [11] are proposed. ISO/IEC 15408 also known as Common Criteria (CC) establishes the concepts, principles and techniques for IT security evaluation. ISO/IEC 18045:2008 is a companion standard of ISO/IEC 15408 and provides a methodology to help an IT security evaluator conduct a CC evaluation by defining the minimum actions to be performed.

- **For SCS risk assessment**, ISO 2800x series of standards [12] was utilised. These standards were used to capture the requirements that need to be addressed by the organisations in order to establish a management system to assure the quality or security of the aspects involved in the supply chain industry. When it comes to security controls, even though the ISO/IEC 27005 [13] and ISO 28000 series provide a very good basis they could not fully encapsulate the details for the present scheme. Having said that, the proposed scheme also considered other families of standards such as NIST's SP 2000 [14] which provide more focused controls for Federal supply chains extending the scheme application directives.

We consider the interplay and compliance of these standards to simplify the evaluation process.

CYRENE proposed the development of an Information Security Management System (ISMS) for the SCS based on ISO2800x and ISO2700x. An online certified SCS-ISMS will be operated by the SCS provider in collaboration with the business partners and it will support the SCS risk and conformity assessment processes. In particular the SCS-ISMS can be a useful tool to the SCS provider and business partners to perform their risk assessment and update their SCS-security policy and the SCS Protection Profile (PP) with all security requirements. The SCS-ISMS can also be used by the accessor during the conformity assessment process to find the necessary evidence to assess the security requirements (claims in the SCS-PP) and evaluate the controls implemented if they

meet the corresponding security requirements throughout specified period.

Assurance Levels

CYRENE-EUSCS covers a wide range of security requirements, by offering all three (3) security assurance levels (AL) defined in the EUCSA (basic, substantial, and high). The AL of the SCS depend on how important or essential a SCS can be according to NIS 2 directive. In particular, Table I below shows a mapping of SCS Provider (SCS-P)

TABLE I
MAPPING SCS-P TO THE INDUSTRIAL SECTORS

SCS-P	Industrial sectors of essential and important services
Operator of Important Services (OIS)	1. Postal and courier services, 2. Waste Management, 3. Manufacture, production and distribution of chemicals, 4. Food production, processing and distribution, 5. Manufacturing, 6. Digital Providers
Operator of Essential Services (OES)	1. Energy (electricity, oil, gas), 2. Transport (air, rail, water, road), 3. Banking, 4. Financial market infrastructures, 5. Health (including hospitals and private clinics), 6. Drinking water supply and distribution, 7. Waste Water, 8. Digital infrastructure, 9. Public Administration, 10. Space

TABLE II
MAPPING EUSCS ALs TO THE SCS

AL (EUSCS)	CYRENE Assurance of SCS
Basic	SCS is neither an essential nor important service according to NIS 2 Directive. The SCS-P is not a provider of essential services (according to NIS).
Substantial	SCS is an important service according to NIS 2 Directive. The SCS-P is a provider of important services (according to NIS).
Substantial	SCS is an essential service according to NIS and European (the SCS-BPs involved are only EU) The SCS-P is a provider of essential services (according to NIS).
High	SCS is an international essential NIS service (including non EU SCS business partners) and the SCS-Provider is a provider of essential (international) services
High	SCS is a military / defense service. The SCS provider is a provider of essential service (national security, law enforcement)

to the industrial sectors of essential and important services where Table II a mapping of the ALs based on the SCS criticality.

As specified in the EUCSA's Article 52(5), assurance level **Basic** is "intended to minimise the known basic risks of

incidents and cyberattacks" and can be further defined as follows: AL Basic should provide limited assurance that the SCS is built and operated with procedures and mechanisms to meet the corresponding security requirements at a level intended to minimize the known basic risks of incidents and cyberattacks. AL Basic should be suitable for SCS components that are designed to meet typical security requirements on services for non-critical data and systems. The typical attacker profile for AL Basic should be a single person with basic scored profile [15], [16] where necessary traits (capabilities, objectives, motives, resources, psychological and behavioural) are limited; for example the hacker cannot repeat a known attack but can perform social engineering attacks. The evaluation scope for AL Basic shall be defined by the description of the SCS and by the security objectives and requirements pertaining to assurance level Basic. The evaluation depth for AL Basic shall be driven by a predefined audit plan.

As specified in the EUCSA's Article 52(6), assurance level **Substantial** is "intended to minimise the known cybersecurity risks, and the risk of incidents and cyberattacks carried out by actors with limited skills and resources" and can be further defined as follows:

AL Substantial should provide reasonable assurance through evaluation by an assessor that the SCS is built and operated with procedures and mechanisms to minimise known cybersecurity risks, and the risk of incidents and cyberattacks carried out by actors with limited skills and resources. The assessor shall determine that the SCS provider has assessed those risks and implemented suitable controls that, if operating effectively, minimize those risks and meet the corresponding security requirements throughout a specified period.

AL Substantial should be suitable for SCS that are designed to meet typical security requirements on services for business-critical data and systems.

The typical attacker profile for AL Substantial should be a person(s) with a moderate score profile where most necessary traits are substantial; in particular substantial traits include the hacking abilities and access to a wide range of known hacking techniques such as penetration testing, including social engineering, but with limited resources, in particular to launch wide attacks or to discover previously unknown vulnerabilities.

The evaluation scope for AL Substantial shall be defined by the description of the SCS and by the security objectives and requirements pertaining to assurance level Substantial.

The evaluation depth for AL Substantial shall include, in

addition to the requirements for assurance level Basic, on-site audit including interviews and inspecting samples, plus a verification that the implementation follows the specified processes and design, including the validation of the functional tests performed on that implementation. As specified in the EUCSA's Article 52(7), assurance level High is "intended to minimise the risk of state-of-the-art cyberattacks carried out by actors with significant skills and resources" and can be further defined as follows:

AL High should provide reasonable assurance through evaluation by an accessor that the SCS is built and operated with procedures and mechanisms to minimise the risk of state-of-the-art cyberattacks carried out by actors with high score profile. The accessor shall determine that the SCS provider has assessed those risks and implemented suitable controls that operated effectively to minimize those risks and meet the corresponding security requirements throughout a specified period.

Assurance level High should be suitable for SCS that are designed to meet specific (exceeding level'substantial') security requirements for critical SCS services (e.g. military, financial sectors).

The typical attacker profile for assurance level High should be a person or a team of persons with a high score profile, most traits are highly scored, in particular the capabilities and resources with access to significant resources to design and perform attacks, get insider access, discover or buy access to previously unknown vulnerabilities.

The evaluation scope for assurance level High shall be defined by the description of the SCS and by the security objectives and requirements pertaining to assurance level High. The evaluation depth for assurance level High shall be driven by a full justification of the coverage for all mappings, including for processes. It may also include higher expectations for some processes and their implementation, as defined in the security controls pertaining to AL High. Finally for assurance level High SCS: the attack paths need to be concretely modelled, the propagation of the vulnerabilities need to be estimated.

Evaluation Methods and Criteria

The EUSCS scheme uses a set of evaluation criteria defined in security objectives and requirements set for Supply Chains. The EUSCS assessment methodology is based on the ISO17065 standard [17]. This methodology defines two assessment approaches that may be used by accessors:

- An assessment approach that may be used for ALs Substantial and High. This approach is inspired from both the ISO17021 [18] standard and the ISAE family of

TABLE III
COVERAGE OF ARTICLE 51 BY REQUIREMENT CATEGORIES

Security objectives from Article 51	Security Objectives and Requirements for SCSs
(a) to protect stored, transmitted or otherwise processed data against accidental or unauthorised storage, processing, access or disclosure during the entire life cycle of the ICT product, ICT service or ICT process;	This is covered in many categories of the scheme, including in particular the CKM category (covering cryptography) and the Communication Security (CS) category (covering the security of communications)
(b) that authorised persons, programs or machines are able only to access the data, services or functions to which their access rights refer;	This is mostly covered by the Identity Access Management (IAM) category (covering identity management, authentication, and access control)
(c) to identify and document known dependencies and vulnerabilities; services or functions have been accessed, used or otherwise processed, at what times and by whom;	This is mostly covered by the PM category (defining relationships with suppliers) and the OPS category (defining vulnerability handling) the OPS category (defining logging)
(e) to verify that ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes do not contain known vulnerabilities;	This is mostly covered by the OPS category (defining general pen testing measures) and by the DEV category (defining vulnerability testing in the development context)
(f) to restore the availability and access to data, services and functions in a timely manner in the event of a physical or technical incident;	This is mostly covered by the Business Continuity Management (BCM) category (defining business continuity) and the Physical Security (PS) category (defining physical security measures)
(g) that ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes are secure by default and by design;	This is mostly covered in the DEV category (defining methodology), with complements in many other categories

(h) that ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes are provided with up-to-date software and hardware that do not contain publicly known vulnerabilities, and are provided with mechanisms for secure updates.

This is mostly covered by the OPS category (vulnerability handling), in the CCM category (for change management) and in the DEV category (for development methodologies)

standards IAASB Handbook [19]

- An assessment approach that may be used solely for assurance level Basic.

CSA highlights that a European cybersecurity certification scheme shall contain evaluation criteria and methods capable of demonstrating the security objectives of article 51. Following the methodologies, Table III below provides a high-level vision based of the coverage of Article 51 requirements by presenting specific security objectives and requirements defined for SCs.

Compliance Monitoring

This section describes the rules for monitoring compliance of SCs security requirements with the ones described by the proposed CYRENE-EUSCS proposed scheme. The requirements met in these rules tend to prevent a set of non-compliant applications and conditions, including but not limited to, the satisfaction of obligations in the context of the SCS certificate, the identification of major security incidents that could potentially lead to a data breach or leak of sensitive information, and the identification of existing or new vulnerabilities with adverse impact upon the SCS security mechanisms. The assessment of the SCS service will be conducted either by an independent assessor (for Assurance Level Basic SCS) or by a CAB (for Assurance Level Substantial/High SCS).

Non-compliance elements:

- Information mismatch between the supplied version of the certificate to the assessor and the version which has been established in the currently running environment.
- Deviation in the requirements met within a certificate content and the supplementary information required for that certification in terms of its format, documentation, and management aspects.
- Irregularities regarding the certification validity requirements including the inability to proceed with maintenance activities, enforce the supplied terms and conditions of the certificate, or deviate from the certified development and operating services.

Vulnerability Handling and Disclosure

The assurance level of the SCS implies the depth of the vulnerability assessment, i.e. SCS of assurance level basic, the accessor will rely upon the claims, vulnerability reports, treatment plans and implementation reports of controls as provided by the SCS provider, technical vulnerability assessment /penetration testing is optional or high level. For assurance level high, the accessor will perform technical vulnerability assessment and penetration testing of all SCS assets and implemented controls. In this section, the rules regarding the way that the previously undetected cybersecurity vulnerabilities in SCs shall be reported and handled are presented.

SCS Providers shall make use of the provisions of ISO/IEC 30111 [20] for a reference of the steps involved for the handling of vulnerabilities. Such steps include the following main phases: preparation, receipt, verification, remediation development, release, post release. New vulnerability information can become available in a variety of ways. The most common ways of receiving information about new vulnerabilities include:

- From the SCS provider and or the SCS partners of according to Article 55.1.(c) of the EUCSA;
 - there is a new publicly disclosed vulnerability on the referenced online repositories (e.g. NIST) according to Article 55.1.(d) of the EUCSA;
 - the SCS provider finds out a related vulnerability to its certified SCS in any other way (e.g. Dark Web).

SCS providers may use the ISO/IEC 29147 standard [21] as a reference for the general rules related to vulnerability disclosure. For the duration of the vulnerability analysis process, the SCS provider may apply an embargo period, meaning that the possible vulnerability is not further disclosed for a period no longer than ninety (90) days. Once a remediation strategy has been defined by the SCS provider and approved by the assessor, information related to the confirmed vulnerability shall be disclosed to the NCCA (in case of Substantial/High AL SCS), in accordance with the reporting standards established by the NCA. The NCCA shall make the reported information available to other NCCAs which may also decide to further investigate the vulnerability. The final step of the disclosure process of a new vulnerability occurs when a correction has been brought to the SCS to mitigate the risk introduced by such vulnerability.

Conclusions

The proposed CYRENE-EUSCS candidate scheme tackles the challenges identified towards the certification of supply chain services, such as a diverse set of relevant SCS stakeholders involved in the life cycle of the certificate (as well as in the life-cycle of the SCS, complex systems and a constantly evolving threat landscape of supply chain services, as well as the existence of different schemes in Member States by calling for cybersecurity best practices across three levels of assurance and by allowing for a transition from current national schemes in the EU. The proposed scheme can be used by a self-assessor or by a CAB depending upon the assurance level of the SCS.

Our future research work aims to apply the proposed scheme in different SCS from various sectors (e.g. maritime, health).

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References

- [1] CYRENE EU H2020 project. Online available: <https://www.cyrene.eu>, accessed on May 14, 2021.
- [2] ENISA, "Cybersecurity Certification EUCC, a candidate cybersecurity certification scheme to serve as a successor to the existing SOG-IS", v1.0, July 2020, Online available: <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/cybersecurity-certification-eucc-candidate-scheme>, accessed on April 29, 2021.
- [3] ENISA, "EUCCS – Cloud Service Scheme: a candidate cybersecurity certification scheme for cloud services". Online available: <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/euccs-cloud-service-scheme>, accessed on April 29, 2021.
- [4] European Parliament and Council, Regulation (EU)2019/881 on ENISA and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act), April 2019.
- [5] The Directive on security of network and information systems (NIS Directive). (2020, December 16). An official website of the European Union. Retrieved July 18, 2021, from <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/directive-security-network-and-information-systems-nis-directive>
- [6] P. Kyranoudi, E. Kalogeraki, A. Michota, D. Polemi, "Cybersecurity Certification Requirements for Supply Chain Services", 26th IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC 2021), Athens, Greece, September 5-8, 2021
- [7] CYRENE EU H2020 project. D2.1 - Supply Chain Analysis and Requirements, 2021.
- [8] ENISA, "Methodology for a Sectoral Cybersecurity Assessment", Online available: <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/methodology-for-a-sectoral-cybersecurity-assessment>, accessed on September 13, 2021.
- [9] ISO/IEC 27000-series on Information Security. Online available: <https://www.iso.org/news/ref2266.html>, accessed on April 29, 2021.
- [10] ISO/IEC 15408-1/2/3:2008-09, international standard, "Information technology-Security techniques-Evaluation criteria for IT security".
- [11] ISO/IEC 18045:2008 international standard, "Information technology-Security techniques- Methodology for IT security evaluation", online available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/46412.html>, accessed on April 29, 2021.
- [12] ISO 28000:2007 international standard, "Specification for security management systems for the supply chain", 1st Edition 2007-09. Online available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/44641.html>, accessed on April 20, 2021.
- [13] ISO/IEC 27005:2018, Information technology — Security techniques — Information security risk management.
- [14] NIST Special Publication 2000-02, Conformity Assessment Considerations for Federal Agencies, online available at: <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.2000-02>
- [15] K. Kioskli, D.Polemi "Psychosocial Approach to Cyber Threat Intelligence", International Journal of Chaotic Computing (IJCC), Volume 7, Issue 1, 2020
- [16] CYRENE EU H2020 project. D3.1 - Conformity Evaluation Process & Multi Level Evidence Driven Supply Chain Risk Assessment, 2021.
- [17] ISO/IEC 17065:2012. Conformity assessment — Requirements for bodies certifying products, processes and services
- [18] ISO/IEC 17021-1:2015, Conformity assessment — Requirements for bodies providing audit and certification of management systems — Part 1: Requirements
- [19] International Standard on Assurance Engagements (ISAE) 3402 Assurance reports on controls at a service organization, in [IAASB Handbook], Vol. 2, pp. 217-264]
- [20] ISO/IEC 30111, Information technology — Security techniques — Vulnerability handling processes
- [21] ISO/IEC 29147:2018, Information technology — Security techniques — Vulnerability disclosure
- [22] CYSMET EU H2020 project. Online available: accessed on May 14, 2021.

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CV

https://docs.google.com/document/pub?id=1qofU6ya50i_uSCipszWbxUgYyUMQFRRoute3FV4s6sFw